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Work Package WP8

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List of Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CIL	Controller-in-the-Loop
CuRFB	copper-based Redox Flow Battery
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
EV	Electric Vehicle
GPT	General Power Theory
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HV	High Voltage
IED	Intelligent Electronic Devices
LV	Low Voltage
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MV	Medium Voltage
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PRBS	Pseudo-Random Binary-Sequence
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
RI	Research Infrastructure
SIPS	System Integrity Protection Scheme
SoC	State of Charge
TA	Trans-national Access
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UP	User Project

Executive Summary

This report presents a detailed analysis of the Trans-national Access (TA) facilities TA2 and their role in supporting advanced research in energy systems integration and validation. It begins by outlining the purpose and structure of the document, setting the stage for a comprehensive review of the user projects hosted by TA2 Research Infrastructures. A breakdown of the user projects distributed across the TA2 Research Infrastructures. These projects are analysed from different perspectives: their scientific focus and key features, such as objects under test and targeted end users of the research. The report highlights how the facilities have enabled a diverse range of experimental and validation activities, supporting both academic and industrial innovation.

The document also features a carefully chosen selection of exemplary projects, showcasing impactful work from both industry, academia and research institutions. These examples illustrate the practical applications and scientific contributions made possible by the TA2 infrastructures. The report concludes with key lessons learned from the hosted projects, offering insights into operational best practices and areas for improvement.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

Trans-national Access (TA) activities were performed in ERIGrid 2.0. The general rules and conditions of the ERIGrid 2.0 laboratory access scheme have been described in (Rodríguez, Vogel, & Strasser, 2021). The TA program for ERIGrid 2.0 has been summarised in the first part of (Rodríguez, Acosta, & Strasser, 2023). This report presents the highlights of the TA with respect to smart energy systems integration and validation defined as TA2. During TA2, users from European and non-European international entities were granted free access to smart grid laboratories of Research Infrastructures (RIs) that are members of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. A selected group of user projects were presented in two conference workshops (Rodríguez et al., 2023) and (Rodríguez et al., 2025). This report presents relevant scientific, technical information and the lessons learned from the infrastructures that implemented user projects hosted in TA2 member laboratories.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 lists the facilities and the user projects implemented in TA2, Section 3 describes scientific areas of focus and features of user projects hosted at TA2 facilities, Section 4 presents the exemplary projects, and describes the lessons learned from implementing the user projects in TA2 from the perspective of achievements and improvements in lab infrastructure or methods of validation. Conclusions and future work are outlined in Section 5.

2 Overview of TA2 Facilities and User Projects

2.1 Facilities

User projects were hosted in ten research facilities organised under TA2. Table 1 summarises the facilities, the number of user projects implemented in each as well as the total number of users and access days delivered.

At the conclusion of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, a total of 735 access days were provided to the user groups over a total of 53 projects under the TA2 Work Package (WP). More details about the scientific areas of focus and features of the projects can be found in Section 3.

Table 1: TA2 RI facilities and provided access statistics.

Project Partner	Installation (RI)	No. of User Projects	Total Number of Users Hosted	Total Number of Access Days
AIT	SmartEST	11	29	217
DTU	SYSLAB/ ESSL	9	27	85
JRC	SGILAB-PTT	1	2	5
JRC	SGILAB-IPR	6	12	63
OFFIS	SESA-Lab	5	6	85
OCT	UDEX	2	3	45
UCY	LVEM	3	5	27
UoS	PNDC	7	16	60
VTT	MultiPower	7	17	128
KEMA	FPG-Lab	2	6	20
Totals		53	123	735

2.2 Summary of User projects per Facility

Table 2 summarises the TA2 user projects, including information about the user group lead organisation, type of organisation, country of user group, host RI and number of users and access days for each project. Technical reports of the results of the user group projects can be found on the ERIGrid 2.0 website¹.

Table 2: Summary of TA2 projects (I: Industry, A: Academic, R: Research Institute).

TA User Project Ref. No.	TA User Project Acronym	Lead Organisation	Type	Country	Host RI	No. of Users in RI	No. of Access Days
101	DEFINIT 2.0	Depsys	I	Switzerland	PNDC (UoS)	2	5
103	AutonoM	Middle East Technical University	A	Turkey	SYSLAB/ ESSL (DTU)	3	10
105	SES-MGES	Aalborg University	A	Denmark	SESA-lab (OFFIS)	1	27

¹<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects/>

Table 2: (continued)

TA User Project Ref. No.	TA User Project Acronym	Lead Organisation	Type	Country	Host RI	No. of Users in RI	No. of Access Days
107	M-ECHall	Energy City Hall	I	Italy	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	2	9
115	DeMaDsVal	AIT	R	Austria	PNDC (UoS)	1	19
116	GRIDPV100	Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology and FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy	R	Cyprus and Malta	Smart EST (AIT)	2	30
119	PPiF	Grenoble INP	R	France	Multi Power (VTT)	2	17
121	VaFlexPot	TU Dortmund University	A	Germany	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	1	9
123	PVinPS	AGH University of Science and Technology	A	Poland	Smart EST (AIT)	3	10
123	PVinPS	AGH University of Science and Technology in Krakow	A	Poland	FPG-Lab (KEMA)	3	10
123	PVinPS	AGH University of Science and Technology in Krakow	A	Poland	LVEM (UCY)	3	5
127	VEHICLE	Zurich University of Applied Science; Ricerca Sistema Energetico; CanmrtENERGY, Natural Resources Canada (NRCan); University of Strathclyde	A	Switzerland, Italy, Canada, UK	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	6	12
131	AIDGRIDS	FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy	R	Cyprus	Smart EST (AIT)	3	8
131	AIDGRIDS	University of Cyprus; Austrian Institute of Technology	A, R	Cyprus; Austria	LVEM (UCY)	2	12

Table 2: (continued)

TA User Project Ref. No.	TA User Project Acronym	Lead Organisation	Type	Country	Host RI	No. of Users in RI	No. of Access Days
132	CybTEST	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Alahabad; Ostfold University College	R, A	India; Norway	Multi Power (VTT)	3	20
134	SMPS	IIT Guwahati	R	India	Smart EST (AIT)	3	22
135	AGIPDem	University of Cape Town	A	South Africa	PNDC (UoS)	2	6
142	CYPRESS	Lahore University of Management Sciences	A	Pakistan	Smart EST (AIT)	2	34
143	RELENDER	Politecnico di Milano	A	Italy	SGILAB-PTT (JRC)	2	5
147	EMS4GCHS	Dicle University; University of Kurdistan	A	Turkey, Iran	SESA-lab (OFFIS)	2	15
150	PERFECT	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad; Ostfold University College	R, A	India, Norway	Multi Power (VTT)	1	20
154	DynaPEM	Tafila Technical University	A	Jordan	Multi Power (VTT)	3	8
158	FaultTS	ENEIDA.IO	I	Portugal	PNDC (UoS)	3	5
160	CTCPM	University of Kurdistan	A	Iran	SESA-lab (OFFIS)	1	15
166	ITCMPD	Tallinn University of Technology	A	Estonia	UDEX (OCT)	1	24
168	Cold Harmonics	University of Strathclyde	A	UK	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	2	10
172	HVLD	ENEIDA.IO	I	Portugal	PNDC (UoS)	3	5
177	CO-FLEX	EPFL	I	Italy	SESA-lab (OFFIS)	1	9
184	HFMPD 4STVSI	Dicle University, University of Kurdistan	A	Turkey	SESA-lab (OFFIS)	1	19
186	MOVES	Hamburg University of Technology	A	Germany	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	3	9
188	PLANREC	Fabbrica Digitale, City of Magliano Alpi	I	Italy	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	1	7

Table 2: (continued)

TA User Project Ref. No.	TA User Project Acronym	Lead Organisation	Type	Country	Host RI	No. of Users in RI	No. of Access Days
198	TwinNET	1: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece; 2: Democritus University of Thrace	A	Greece	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	2	10
201	M4Grid	AGH University of Science and Technology in Krakow	A	Poland	FPG-Lab (KEMA)	3	10
202	RTT-Flow	Aarhus University, Denmark	A	Denmark	Smart EST (AIT)	2	27
204	DiSeCTER	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany	R	Germany	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	2	10
206	CGNN4Grid	Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Norway	A	Norway	Smart EST (AIT)	2	6
207	IaaS Platform	German Aerospace Center (DLR) - Institute of Networked Energy Systems	R	Germany	Multi Power (VTT)	5	20
210	RCPIN	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	R	Sweden	Smart EST (AIT)	3	30
212	EARLYFAULT MONITORING	Ampacimon SA	I	Belgium	UDEX (OCT)	2	21
213	EXPLORE-MP3S	University of Split - FESB	A	Croatia	Smart EST (AIT)	3	24
215	RESIDE	University of Trento	A	Italy	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	2	20
216	RECDT	fabbricadigitale S.r.l.	I	Italy	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	2	7
218	DRE4 Balance Reserve	Technische Hochschule Ulm	A	Germany	Smart EST (AIT)	5	11
220	RECORD	Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico	R	Italy	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	3	10
222	BN	ENEIDA.IO	I	Portugal	PNDC (UoS)	3	5
224	FLUCCOM	KU Leuven	A	Belgium	Multi Power (VTT)	2	23

Table 2: (continued)

TA User Project Ref. No.	TA User Project Acronym	Lead Organisation	Type	Country	Host RI	No. of Users in RI	No. of Access Days
236	REMOTEC	POLIMI	A	Italy	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	3	10
240	WASIPS	OFFIS	R	Germany	PNDC (UoS)	2	15
242	LIVABLE-LV	Østfold University College	A	Norway	LVEM (UCY)		10
243	DARC PV	KU Leuven	A	Belgium	SGILAB-IPR (JRC)	2	10
244	RENEWIES	Cumhuriyet University	A	Turkey	Smart EST (AIT)	1	15
247	5G-SmartPV	RWTH Aachen Universität	A	Germany	Multi Power (VTT)	1	20
253	HyStorization	INSEC TEC	R	Portugal	SYSLAB/ESSL (DTU)	3	5

3 Analysis of User Projects Hosted at TA2 Facilities

This section analyses some of the scientific areas of focus of the TA2 user projects and highlights some common features gleaned from the projects' technical reports.

3.1 Scientific Areas covered by TA2 Projects

The scientific areas of the TA2 user projects represented in the word cloud of Figure 1 revolve around the modernisation and transformation of the Distribution Power System. It captures a multidisciplinary approach to future energy systems by showcasing various interconnected focus areas, primarily within smart grid technologies, renewable energy integration, grid reliability, and digital transformation.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the relevant scientific areas in TA2 user projects.

Figure 1 highlights several key insights into the scientific scope of TA2 user projects. The central scientific area is clearly the “Distribution Power System,” suggesting it as the primary area of investigation. Among these are terms that represent essential technologies and challenges in modern distribution networks, such as Microgrids, Renewable Energy, Battery Energy Storage Systems, Electric Vehicles, and Photovoltaic (PV) Generation, all of which reflect a broader transition toward decentralised and renewable energy integration. The emphasis on “Low Carbon Technologies” underscores the critical role of decarbonisation in shaping future grid infrastructures. Grid management and control are increasingly reliant on intelligent systems, as indicated by references to Control Systems, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven tools, Predictive Controllers, and Energy Prediction.

Reliability and security also emerge as major concerns, with concepts such as fault detection, monitoring systems, cybersecurity, and frequency containment reserves highlighting the need for resilience against operational faults and cyber threats. Physical infrastructure remains foundational, evidenced by the mention of transformers, high voltage grids, and the design of distribution power systems. Finally, flexibility is highlighted as a key requirement for modern

grids, enabling them to adapt to fluctuating demand and the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources.

3.2 Key Features of TA2 projects

The following subsections outline and describe four key features of the TA2 user projects: *targeted end users testing devices, voltage level specifications, and the application of machine learning/artificial intelligence.*

Targeted End Users

Figure 2 illustrates the key end users targeted by the TA2 user projects' outcomes. The targeted end users are diverse, including energy management aggregators, smart grid operators, and electricity grid operators, who coordinate the flow and balance of electricity. Complementing them are renewable energy communities, distribution and Low Voltage (LV) grid operators, and Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) operators, all playing vital roles in localised generation, distribution, and storage. Supporting technologies are provided by PV inverter manufacturers and system designers, while flexibility services and network aggregators enhance grid responsiveness and efficiency. Finally, cybersecurity controller designers to ensure the digital infrastructure remains secure. Collectively, these actors enable a decentralised, resilient, and sustainable energy system by integrating digital tools, storage, renewables, and secure operations.

Figure 2: Target end users of TA2 user group projects.

Objects under Test

Figure 3 illustrates a variety of advanced tools and technologies that have been tested within a hosted laboratory environment. The testing facilities serve as a platform for validating and integrating a broad range of solutions relevant to smart grid and energy system operations. These include hardware-based systems like microgrid central controller hardware, Electric Vehicle (EV) charging control tools, alongside software-based solutions such as forecasting software, inertial control software, and sequential service restoration algorithms. The testing also includes optimisation and control algorithms, including voltage regulation, optimal scheduling, and stochastic multi-objective optimisation, as well as monitoring and diagnostic tools such as fault detection algorithms, partial discharge measurements, and power distribution system fault monitors.

Additionally, platforms like TransiEnt-library and Infrastructure-as-a-Service provide simulation and deployment capabilities, while flexibility-oriented tools (e.g., flexibility open-source tool, demand flexibility tool) support dynamic grid responsiveness. Collectively, these components demonstrate the comprehensive and integrated testing capabilities of the RIs to support the advancement of resilient, intelligent, and flexible energy systems.

Figure 3: Objects under test in the TA2 user group projects.

Additional Project Features

Additional features of TA2 user projects can also be identified. Two are expanded on here – namely, voltage level and the use of Machine Learning/AI. 42 projects considered LV networks

in their scope, with 3 projects considering Medium Voltage (MV)/High Voltage (HV), while 14 projects have not specified the voltage category. Regarding the use of Machine Learning or AI, about 30 TA2 projects reported not using these technologies, 6 confirmed their use, and 22 either did not specify or found it not applicable.

4 Exemplary TA2 Projects and Lessons Learned

4.1 RI Survey

A survey was designed to gather feedback from RIs and to collect detailed information on exemplary projects delivered under the TA2 WP. A comprehensive summary of these exemplary projects is essential to identify the most pressing needs across academia, applied research, and industry sectors. The specific information requested through the survey is outlined in Table 3. The questionnaire was structured into five main sections, each targeting different aspects of user projects, users, and RI experiences.

The first section collected fundamental details about each User Project (UP), including its reference number, acronym, a brief summary, and the classification of the user (Academic, Research Institute, Industry, or Public Sector). The second section assessed whether the project had a groundbreaking or significant impact on the host RI. The third section focused on evaluating the project's exemplary characteristics and the key insights gained by the RI. The fourth section explored the learning outcomes for the users as a result of their engagement with the RI's infrastructure. The final section gathered information on the main outcomes and recommendations derived from hosting the projects, including which technical aspects functioned well and which encountered challenges.

Table 3: Information request per project as part of the RI survey.

Information requested per Project	
1	TA UP Reference Number
2	TA User Project Acronym
3	Brief technical summary of the project
4	User classification (Academic (A), Research Institute (R), Industry (I), Public Sector (P))
5	Do you consider this UP was ground breaking or significantly impactful for he host RI? (yes, no)
6	If UP is ground breaking or impactful. Please, describe what is the new impact/development/solution that the UP helped you to achieve in your RI?
7	Is this an exemplary UP? (yes, no)
8	If the answer is yes for exemplary UP. Please describe: what has your RI learned from the UP?
9	What has the UP learned? What has the UP learned that could not have been achieved without the TA provisions?
10	What are the main outcomes/recommendations from hosting this UP in your RI?
11	What aspects/things worked particularly well during TA provision process (before, during and after UP access)? Technical/Non-technical aspects
12	What aspects/things did not work particularly well during TA provision process (before, during and after UP access)? Technical/Non-technical aspects

The insights from the survey are valuable for supporting RIs to improve project management, technical processes, and user support. The survey enables the RIs to reflect on the methodology, procedures, and management of validation projects. The selection of exemplary projects listed in the subsections below were selected based on the RI survey. Those exemplary projects were indicated as such based on the feedback of the hosting RI and their evaluation of the impact the project had made scientifically and/or the project's contribution to improvements in the RI capabilities or validation methods.

4.2 Exemplary Projects from Industry

Three TA2 projects identified as exemplary from industry, each with a summary of main objectives and work carried out are presented below.

High Voltage Line Down (HVLD)

This project aimed to assess the performance of the algorithm developed by the user group, ENEIDA, can detect and classify fallen conductor faults. In particular, HV overhead line conductors falling on the ground on the load side of the line, which are difficult to detect due to the low fault current value. The ability of the algorithm to distinguish between loss of phase and line down conditions was also tested. The latter poses a higher safety risk to the network operator's assets and the public.

Line down fault and loss of phase scenarios were created in the PNDC (UoS) 11 kV test environment (see Figure 4), while measurements of the network electrical quantities were made with the user group LV monitoring equipment.

Figure 4: HVLD 11 kV and LV test setup.

Several high-impedance fault and phase loss scenarios were carried out in the test network and introduced at different locations in the network. The results were compared against set thresholds to distinguish between the two lines down and phase loss (depicted in Figure 5).

The test capabilities and method offered by the host were essential to the validation of the fault detection algorithm, leading to advancement of the user group solution's Technology Readiness Level (TRL), thus facilitating further field trials. The project suggested that enhancements to the test setup should be considered, including the ability to create higher resistance fault scenarios (i.e., in the kilo-ohms range) at 11 kV.

Figure 5: Test results laid against detection thresholds.

Early detection and location of severe insulation defects and insulation faults in distribution grids through monitoring using GPS synchronised sensors (EARLYFAULTMONITORING)

This project aimed to validate a monitoring system developed by the user group (Ampacimon) to detect, classify and locate insulation and pre-faults and faults in HV grids. The measurement system and associated sensors were installed in the UDEX (OCT) lab (example depicted in Figure 6).

Figure 6: Example test setup and sensor installation.

A range of test scenarios were carried out to verify the performance of the sensor system (including 50Hz and high frequency sensors), namely:

- Transient fault injection simulating HV switching (example capture shown in Figure 7), lightning and cable sheath short circuits,
- Short circuit clearance operation via protection, and
- High short circuit current withstand tests of installed sensors.

Figure 7: Signals captured by sensor system during an HV switching test.

The unique test facilities offered by the host enabled the execution of realistic test scenarios, enabling the verification of the use group's solution. The data collected during testing will be used by the user group to further develop their solution, including firmware updates to fine-tune detection thresholds for more accurate event classification.

Renewable Energy Communities Digital Twin (RECDT)

This project aimed to validate the ability to predict individual household power consumption purely based on socio-economic data and in the absence of historical power consumption data. The user group, fabbricadigitale, developed an AI model to generate the household power consumption forecast.

The user group developed their database (see Figure 8) in a format such that it is easily deployable and usable by others via Python notebooks and a containerised Postgres database.

Figure 8: Entity relationship model diagram of developed database.

The host, SGILAB-IRP (JRC), enabled the user to identify available and suitable data sets for building their model as well validate the model outcomes. It is important to note that this project

was a follow-up of two earlier projects M-ECHall and PLANREC, emphasising the role of the TA programme in advancing research and development of the user groups over the lifetime of the ERIGRID 2.0 project. Areas of improvement were highlighted in the project, including the need for larger and more detailed data sets to enable clustering and improved training of the AI models.

4.3 Exemplary Projects from Research Institutions

Three TA2 projects identified as exemplary from research institutions, each with a summary of main objectives and work carried out are presented below.

Data Driven Detection of Malfunctioning Devices in Power Distribution Systems Validation (DeMaDsVal)

This project aimed to validate a framework for the surveillance of the network to allow network operators to identify misconfiguration/misbehaviour of connected devices that provide grid support services (e.g., inverter-based distributed generation). The decentralised approach to the increasing connection of such devices and the lack of distribution network observability emphasises the need for such tools.

An experiment for gathering data from distribution networks and connected devices (i.e., PV inverters) was set up at PNDC (UoS) using the test LV network and associated assets (e.g. transformers, load banks, acPV generation) as depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: LV network experimental setup.

Various test scenarios were created, including varied load and PV generation profiles. Alterations of the PV inverter control parameters were also introduced, and electrical network data were recorded for all test scenarios. The data was synthesised and fed into an offline simulation model to validate its performance against the real-world collected data and then synthesised (see Figure 10) to fine-tune and validate an offline simulation model that can be used in running scenarios.

The project highlighted the value of enhancing some of the RI capabilities, such as more accessible controllers so that control curves can be adjusted and a wider range of inverter-connected resources in terms of size and type.

Figure 10: Synthesis and comparison of lab collected and simulation produced data.

Wide Area System Integrity Protection Schemes for Digitalized Sub-Stations (WASIPS)

This project aimed to validate the feasibility of using commercial Intelligent Electronic Devices (IED) for the implementation of a Wide Area System Integrity Protection Scheme (SIPS) based on IEC 61850 standard GOOSE messaging. An Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) test setup was used at PNDC (UoS) to implement a real-time network model together with a commercial IED programmed with the SIPS logic developed by the user group as depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: SIPS HIL test setup.

The tests carried out assessed the performance of the SIPS logic underpinned by two communication modes: 1) local GOOSE messaging, and 2) wide area R-GOOSE messaging. The communication latency and response time of the IED protection functions were monitored (Figure 12).

The project yielded valuable experience in programming the commercial IEDs for a bespoke user-defined solution. Furthermore, the host gained more experience in setting up wide area communication networks, including layer 3 multicast routing required for R-GOOSE communication.

Unified Infrastructure-as-a-Service Platform for Distributed Co-Simulation of Networked Microgrids (IaaS Platform)

The project aimed to demonstrate a proof-of-concept test case of the user group IaaS platform. The use case considered was a co-simulation consisting of a grid forming inverter and EV

Figure 12: Monitoring GOOSE messages on the wire.

charging models coupled with a digital real-time simulator and physical load as depicted in Figure 13 and implemented in MultiPower (VTT).

Figure 13: Integrated test environment implemented for validating the software.

Both integration and functional tests were carried out as part of the proof of concept. Tests such as grid frequency disturbances were carried out to observe the response of the co-simulated elements (e.g. as shown in Figure 14).

Key learnings were obtained specifically in relation to the co-simulation step size and its impact on simulation observability and time delays of observed responses of the simulation. This project highlights the contributions of the co-simulation expertise developed over the years by ERIGrid and ERIGrid 2.0 project partners and the value of such validation frameworks in testing physical and virtual components.

Figure 14: Example results of IaaS co-simulation.

4.4 Exemplary Projects from Academia

Five TA2 projects identified as exemplary from academia, each with a summary main objectives and work carried out are presented below.

Resilient Control of Power Inverter Network (RCPIN)

This project aimed to validate a framework of inverter control design based on resilience. The framework defines resilience as the ability to maintain voltage stability under nominal conditions and recover from intermittent violations in a finite time. The validation was carried out using OPAL-RT based HIL at SmartEST (AIT) as depicted in Figure 15.

Figure 15: HIL environment for the resilient controller testing.

Tests were carried out focusing on evaluating the voltage controller’s resilience (i.e., durability and recoverability) under simulated power injection attacks in the grid and comparing the performance against nominal droop control (e.g. see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Comparison of resilient controller performance with droop controller.

The user group identified several challenges, such as the impact of the HIL implementation on signal delays and subsequent controller performance. Some solutions were suggested for implementation, such as code optimisation in the REDIS library. Furthermore, the host gained insights for developing HIL tools.

5G-Driven Edge Computing for Real-Time Monitoring and Control of Photovoltaic Systems in Smart Grids (5G-SmartPV)

The project aimed to design and validate a 5G-enabled PV inverter control system. The project integrated software and hardware elements in an HIL test environment at MultiPower (VTT) as depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17: HIL test setup of 5G based cloud and edge control system.

Closed-loop tests were carried out to evaluate the controller and communication network performance, including round-trip latency over 5G (e.g., Figure 18). Tests demonstrated the viability of the controls over the 5G network.

Figure 18: Edge 5G round trip latency.

The work suggested that future works need to focus on validating the scalability of the communication architecture in the future, extending the validation to include physical inverters in a Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) setup and studying the impact of cyber security vulnerabilities and communication failure modes.

Renewable Energy Communities Optimal Resources Dispatch (RECORD)

This project aimed to validate a coordinated DER controller developed by the user group for Renewable Energy Communities (REC) that is based on a multi-objective optimisation. The validation was carried out in a Controller-in-the-Loop (CIL) setup at SGILAB-IPR (JRC) as illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19: CHIL test setup of the controller.

Tests were performed on the RECORD controller as a stand-alone and in the CIL setup. The controller setpoints were issued for a BESS taking into account the REC power flows and BESS State of Charge (SoC). Ultimately, the economic benefit of the developed controller was evaluated for the REC as shown in Figure 20.

The provision of access enabled effective demonstration of the optimised controller capabilities. However, additional value can be derived from future PHIL tests involving physical Distributed Energy Resource (DER) assets as well as evaluating the controller scalability via a remote multi-RI co-simulation.

Figure 20: REC savings costs influenced by the controlled BESS.

Artificial Intelligent Digitalized Solutions for Smart Grids (AIDGRIDS)

This project aimed to validate and demonstrate AI-driven tools that dynamically manage microgrids with high PV generation penetration. The project was implemented in two RIs, LVEM (UCY) and SmartEST (AIT), over two phases using a co-simulation setup as illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Co-simulation setup at both host RIs.

The AI driven digital twin developed by the user group consisted of a state-estimator and net-load forecasting tools. A combination of real-time simulator and real metered data was used to run the test scenarios for validating the performance of the tools (e.g. voltage estimation accuracy was evaluated, Figure 22).

The project highlighted scientific and technological impacts, including validation of the AI tools and demonstrating integration with DER power microgrids. Furthermore, the host RIs gained valuable experience and insights from the project, including learning how to couple software models to enable the co-simulation and how to integrate AI tools into a real-time simulation environment.

Advanced GPT Inverter Physical Demonstration (AGIPDem)

Figure 22: Comparison of actual vs estimated voltage profiles.

This project aimed to characterise the impact on the power system of an inverter operating under General Power Theory (GPT) control. A commercial inverter was retrofitted with an GPT based controller developed by the user group. The testing was carried out at PNDC (UoS), following a phase of HIL testing in DPSL (UoS). The inverter was connected to the LV test network as depicted in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Inverter physical test setup.

A suite of tests was carried out, including variations in loading, load unbalance and injection of harmonic distortion and observing the response of the inverter (example inverter current response in Figure 24).

A few challenges were faced during the implementation of the project, from which the host RI and user group learned a great deal. For example, issues faced with data collection and its consistency made analysing the inverter performance challenging. This leads to improvements in communication of measurement requirements for experiments and setup procedures for the measurement systems used.

Figure 24: Example inverter current response.

4.5 Key Lessons Learned from TA2 User Projects

The lessons learned from each TA2 project, as reported by the hosted labs, were gathered through a survey and categorised based on their primary area of research and development or the methodology used in conducting the project's objectives. These are summarised below.

Hardware-in-the-Loop and Real-Time Simulation

The GRIDPV100 project employed the Typhoon HIL 604 platform to conduct real-time simulations on a Cypriot distribution feeder, demonstrating that aggregating low-rating PV systems into a single controllable unit significantly enhanced system reliability, with minimal frequency and voltage deviations observed during islanded operation. The implementation of virtual inertia-based control further improved transient response, with future efforts focused on developing holistic control strategies for grid-forming PVs and identifying optimal deployment locations within large distribution networks.

At AIT SmartEST, the copper-based Redox Flow Battery (CuRFB) study validated battery models using experimental data and OPAL-RT's RT-LAB HIL simulations, enabling precise performance prediction under dynamic conditions. In converter-dominated microgrids, real-time HIL testing of Pseudo-Random Binary-Sequence (PRBS) harmonic injection techniques facilitated accurate grid impedance estimation and stability margin analysis, supporting robust microgrid design. Additionally, a voltage state estimator was developed using a software-in-the-loop approach, achieving high accuracy (<1% error), while a net-load forecasting model demonstrated strong performance (4% error), collectively enhancing the predictive observability and control capabilities essential for future smart grid operation.

In summary, HIL and real-time simulation platforms afforded rapid development and validation of the technologies and solutions implemented by the user groups.

Optimisation and Model Predictive Control

Testing of Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithms revealed numerical inconsistencies and adaptation challenges, ultimately leading to the decision to drop experimental validation. Despite efforts to optimise performance, the MPC algorithms exhibited elevated Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and low switching frequencies; however, the introduction of delay compensation showed notable improvements in load current THD and input current error. In parallel,

offline optimisation techniques were developed and explored for day-ahead scheduling, successfully identifying optimal bidding strategies and efficient charging/discharging modes to enhance system operational performance.

At AIT SmartEST, islanding and ancillary services tests were carried out on various PV inverters, with results showing that most inverters disconnected upon the loss of the regenerative voltage source, except for one operating in “off-grid” mode under balanced load conditions. Ancillary services testing confirmed compliance with operational standards across multiple control modes, although some power oscillations marginally exceeded prescribed limits.

In summary, RI based validation played an important role in establishing the readiness of prototypes and new control algorithms, highlighting the need for further improvements for the user groups to carry out.

Cybersecurity and Communication

The exploration of cyber-attack resilience in PV systems emphasised the importance of understanding generator behaviour under malicious conditions, which can support the development of effective detection and mitigation strategies. While the impact of cyber-attacks on PV control loops within distributed networks was not directly examined, the work concentrated on implementation within transmission network environments. In parallel, delay-tolerant algorithms were developed for real-time fault location applications, showing promising robustness when operated over 5G networks. Nevertheless, inconsistencies in inverter output under non-ideal conditions present ongoing challenges, highlighting the need for further refinement to ensure reliable performance in dynamic grid scenarios.

In summary, RI capabilities enable the safe and controlled characterisation of cyber threats and communication network resilience necessary for realising future grids.

Energy Storage and Battery Systems

Accurate estimation of BESS efficiency can be achieved through continuous monitoring of the state of charge and exchanged power, offering critical insights for optimising battery performance, operational reliability, and lifecycle longevity. Additionally, advanced control strategies and modelling techniques were developed to address voltage stability challenges at the interconnection points of PV and storage systems. These innovations contribute significantly to enhancing overall grid stability and supporting the integration of renewable energy sources into modern power systems.

In summary, RI capabilities were key to validating new BESS technologies and their grid integration strategies.

Grid Services and Ancillary Functions

The DRE4BalanceReserve project evaluated a CLS gateway application designed to link decentralised PV inverter systems with a central pooling platform to provide frequency balancing reserves. While the system successfully met the prequalification criteria for automatic frequency restoration reserve, including the required response time and performance thresholds, it encountered issues with inconsistent command execution, affecting overall reliability. Complementing this, comprehensive testing was carried out to validate a service restoration framework across various operational scenarios. These included the performance of grid-following inverters with and without grid-support functionalities, centralised automatic gain control for

frequency and voltage regulation, and the effectiveness of distributed secondary control mechanisms during black-start operations, demonstrating the framework's robustness under diverse grid restoration conditions.

In summary, the TA2 offering enabled advancement of user group solutions towards real-world deployment through pre-qualification tests.

Forecasting and Data-Driven Control

The GridFusion approach significantly enhanced probabilistic forecasting accuracy by effectively capturing uncertainties in renewable energy generation and demand variability, while its advanced spatiotemporal modelling, accounting for both spatial and temporal dependencies, demonstrated strong scalability and applicability in real-world energy systems. Complementing this, research into socio-economic metrics revealed that end-user characteristics are reliable predictors of energy consumption behaviour, particularly when analysed over extended time aggregation periods. These insights provide valuable guidance for the design of more targeted and effective demand-side management strategies within modern, data-driven energy networks.

In summary, the test setups offered by the RI allowed a comprehensive scenario-driven validation of the user group algorithms.

Protection and Fault Analysis

The analysis of fault characteristics in hybrid AC-DC converters focused on asymmetrical faults, single pole-to-ground, and pole-to-pole events, revealing critical interactions between AC and DC sides and highlighting limitations in existing protection mechanisms. Using real-time simulations, the study underscored the need for advanced protection algorithms tailored to the complexities of hybrid microgrids. In parallel, significant progress was made in the monitoring of instrument transformers through partial discharge analysis in substations, strengthening diagnostic capabilities and contributing to enhanced maintenance strategies and long-term reliability of high-voltage infrastructure.

In summary, a combination of real-time simulations and physical testing allowed for better characterisation of fault conditions and assets experiencing partial discharge.

Microgrid Stability and Inertia

The study underscored the critical role of inertia response in maintaining stability within microgrids, particularly in systems with low inherent inertia, where optimising the delivery of fast frequency response is essential to enhance resilience and operational performance. Additionally, it was found that enlarging the co-simulation step-size in digital twin environments compromises observability and introduces greater time delays between real and simulated responses. To address these challenges, future work should focus on improving simulation efficiency through advanced code optimisation and the deployment of distributed applications, enabling more accurate and responsive modelling of complex energy systems.

In summary, co-simulations carried out at the host RI revealed gaps and opportunities for improvement in the simulation platforms to enable more accurate and stable studies.

Platform Development and Integration

The Power Networks Demonstration Centre (PNDC) expanded its capabilities by incorporating high-voltage line-down testing into its suite of services, thereby enhancing its ability to support advanced testing and validation of power system resilience and safety measures. Additionally, close collaboration with the mosaik development team during the second user engagement streamlined communication and organisational processes, resulting in more efficient project execution and a stronger foundation for future joint development efforts.

In summary, TA2 activities afforded enhancements in physical and simulation capabilities of host RI.

5 Conclusions

The successfully completed TA2 user projects provided critical insights across diverse technological domains in smart grid research and development. Real-time simulations and HIL testing validated advanced control strategies and enhanced grid monitoring, while optimisation efforts revealed key challenges in MPC deployment. Cybersecurity studies highlighted vulnerabilities in PV systems, stressing the importance of resilient communication frameworks. Progress in battery systems and ancillary grid services demonstrated the potential for improved reliability and flexibility in distributed energy resources. Advanced forecasting models and socio-economic analytics supported more adaptive demand-side management. Protection studies in hybrid systems and microgrid inertia investigations underscored the need for improved stability mechanisms. Lastly, enhanced testing platforms and collaborative development frameworks built a solid foundation for scalable, integrated smart grid solutions.

Future work across the various TA2 projects focuses on enhancing technological robustness, interoperability, and real-world applicability in smart grid environments. Efforts are directed toward improving control systems under uncertain communication and grid conditions (e.g., AutoNoM, CYPRESS), refining model accuracy with real-world variables (Vehicle, DynaPEM), and creating user-friendly, open-source tools enriched with socio-behavioural datasets (M-ECHall). Projects like DeMaDsVal and EMS4GCHS aim to support infrastructure for broader testing capabilities and enable multi-lab collaboration, while projects like AIDGRIDS and PERFECT focus on standardising simulation models and integrating advanced communication protocols to improve interoperability and real-time grid control.

A significant emphasis is placed on cybersecurity, communication resilience, and protection mechanisms. Projects such as CybTEST, CTCPM, and HVLD advocate for simulating and mitigating cyberattacks, incorporating machine learning and interdisciplinary approaches to bolster system reliability. Similarly, efforts in FaultTS and EARLYFAULTMONITORING aim to refine fault detection for high-impedance scenarios and transient disturbances, with active learning and predictive analytics being central to future enhancements. Projects like ITCMPD and RECDT underline the need for more comprehensive datasets and machine learning advancements to enhance predictive maintenance and household consumption modelling.

Further research will also target integrating flexible energy systems and real-time hardware-in-the-loop simulations to support grid stability and decarbonisation goals. Projects like GRIDPV100 and RCPIN explore optimal placement and scalability of grid-forming PVs and control systems, while CO-FLEX, MOVES, and PLANREC emphasise refining demand-flexibility coordination, validating broader system models, and improving forecasting via AI. Projects like RELENDER, FLUCCOM, and RTT-Flow propose advancing remote control capabilities, embedded fault detection devices, and adaptive controllers for grid frequency support, ensuring modern grids remain stable, secure, and adaptable.

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